

Synthesis and biological evaluation of 3-substituted-4-[2'-(4''-isobutylphenyl)propionamido]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and their derivatives

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Several 3-substituted-4-[2'-(4''-isobutylphenyl)propionamido]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and their derivatives have been synthesized. Some compounds have shown promising antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities.

Heterocycles bearing a symmetrical triazole or 1,3,4-thiadiazole ring system are reported to show a broad spectrum of biological activities¹. It is also reported that substituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles show CNS depressant and mild to strong anti-inflammatory activities. In view of these observations and in continuation of our studies on condensed heterocycles, we thought of interest to synthesize certain triazole derivatives and evaluate the biological activities associated with them.

The required 3-substituted-4-[2'-(4''-isobutylphenyl)propionamido]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (**3**) were prepared in excellent yields in one-pot reaction by heating ibuprofen hydrazide [2-(4-isobutylphenyl)propionic acid hydrazide] with potassium dithiocarbazinate (**2**)². Ibuprofen, a well known anti-inflammatory drug, has been incorporated with a view to enhance the activity of triazole derivatives. The acid hydrazides (**1**) required were prepared from the corresponding esters by reaction with hydrazine hydrate³. The reaction of **3** with chloroacetic acid and concentrated sulfuric acid yielded 3-substituted-4-[2'-(4''-isobutylphenyl)propionamido]-*s*-triazolo-5-thioacetic acids (**4**) and 3,5-disubstituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-thiadiazoles (**5**) respectively, in excellent yields.

Results and Discussion

Biological activities : A total of 19 compounds **3a**₂-**a**₄, **a**₆, **a**₇, **a**₉-**a**₁₂, **a**₁₅, **4a**₃, **a**₆, **a**₇, **a**₉, **a**₁₁, **a**₁₂, **a**₁₅, **5a**₂ and **a**₁₁ were screened for *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities against different strains of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria such as *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and fungus *A. niger* by cup-plate method⁴ using concentrations 50 and 100 µg ml⁻¹. The solvent used was DMSO.

- a**₁ Phenyl
- a**₂ 2-Chlorophenyl
- a**₃ 4-Chlorophenyl
- a**₄ 4-Nitrophenyl
- a**₅ 3,5-Dinitrophenyl
- a**₆ 2-Aminophenyl
- a**₇ 4-Aminophenyl
- a**₈ Phenoxyethyl

- a**₉ 2-Methylphenoxyethyl
- a**₁₀ 3-Methylphenoxyethyl
- a**₁₁ 4-Methylphenoxyethyl
- a**₁₂ 4-Aminophenoxyethyl
- a**₁₃ 2-Nitrophenoxyethyl
- a**₁₄ 2-Naphthoxyethyl
- a**₁₅ 4-Naphthoxyethyl

It is observed that **3a**₂, **3a**₆, **4a**₆ and **4a**₁₂ (17–20, 18–22 mm) have comparable activity with penicillin and streptomycin against *B. subtilis* (17, 21 mm) and (18, 20 mm) while **3a**₂, **3a**₁₅, **4a**₁₂ (14–16 mm) have comparable activity with streptomycin against *E. coli* (14, 16 mm). Rest of the compounds showed moderate activity with penicillin and streptomycin against the same organisms. Compounds **3a**₃, **3a**₁₁, **3a**₁₂ (15–17, 19–21 mm) have comparable activity

with griseofulvin (15, 19 mm) against *A. niger*.

Although no conclusive structure-activity relationship has emerged from the antimicrobial screening, it appears that 3 aryl/aryloxy substituent plays some role in determining the activity of the compounds. The active ones have 2-chlorophenyl, 2-aminophenyl, 4-methylphenoxyethyl, 2-naphthoxyethyl, 4-chlorophenyl, 4-aminophenoxyethyl as substituent at position-3 of the triazole ring. At this stage it is rather difficult to hypothesize on the relative influence of the triazole moiety on the activity of the compounds.

Anti-inflammatory activity : Compounds **3a₉**, **3a₁₁**, **3a₁₂** and **5a₁₁** were assessed for anti-inflammatory activity at 100 mg kg⁻¹ oral dose by acute formalin-induced oedema in rat paw following the reported technique⁵. Compound **3a₁₁** having 4-methylphenoxyethyl as substituent at 3-position of the triazole ring possesses significant activity (inhibition 45.77%) while other compounds exhibit mild activity when compared with a standard drug ibuprofen (inhibition 46%). Thus the conversion of **3a₁₁** to **5a₁₁** has reduced the anti-inflammatory activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 8000 spectrophotometer, PMR spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a EM 390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Hewlett-Packard 5970 G.C. spectrometer. Purity of compounds in addition to the elemental analysis was checked by TLC using silica gel G. All the compounds showed satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H and N.

3-Substituted-4-[2'-(4''-isobutylphenyl)propionamido]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (3a₁₂) : Potassium dithiocarbazinate (**2a₁₂**) and ibuprofen hydrazide were heated in equimolar proportions in an oil-bath at 170–180° for 8 h, when profuse evolution of H₂S was observed. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with cold water and acidified with conc. HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallized from aqueous ethanol : **3a₁₂** (74%), m.p. 135° (Found : C, 62.02; H, 6.29; N, 16.40. C₂₂H₂₇O₂N₅S calcd. . C, 62.11; H, 6.35; N, 16.47%); ν_{max} 3240 (NH₂), 2930 (OCH₂), 1660 (CONH), 1600 (C=N), 1475 (NH C=S), 1370 (C-N), 1200 (C=S), 1010 (-O-), 870 cm⁻¹ (disubstituted benzene); δ 0.9 (6H, d, 2 × CH₃ of CH(CH₃)₂), 1.3 (3H, d, CH₃ of CHCH₃), 1.8 (1H, m, CH of CH(CH₃)₂), 2.4 (2H, d, CH₂ of CH₂CH(CH₃)₂), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂ of OCH₂), 3.7 (1H, q, CH of OCCHCH₃), 6.0 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.0–7.4 (8H, m, ArH), 10.0 (1H, s, NH of CONH); m/z 426, 309, 274, 252, 231, 212, 191, 176, 162, 132, 99, 81 and 65. Similarly, other compounds (**3a₁**-**a₁₁**, **a₁₃**-**a₁₅**, yields (65–87%)) were prepared and crystallized from

aqueous ethanol : **3a₁**, m.p. 205°, **a₂**, 278°, **a₃**, 308°, **a₄**, 184°, **a₅**, 220°, **a₆**, 228°, **a₇**, 222°, **a₈**, 120°, **a₉**, 172°, **a₁₀**, 168°, **a₁₁**, 196°, **a₁₃**, 232°, **a₁₄**, 168°, **a₁₅**, 251°

3-Substituted-4-[2'-(4''-isobutylphenyl)propionamido]-5-thioacetic acids (4a₁₂) : Equimolar proportions of **3a₁₂** and chloroacetic acid were dissolved in ethanol containing 3-4 drops of pyridine and refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallized from aqueous ethanol **4a₁₂** (70%), m.p. 164° (Found : C, 58.60; H, 6.04; N, 14.38. C₂₄H₂₉O₄N₅S calcd. C, 58.62; H, 6.00; N, 14.44%); ν_{max} 3240 (NH₂), 3100 (OH of COOH), 2930 (OCH₂), 1660 (CONH), 1545 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1010 cm⁻¹ (-O-); δ 0.9 (6H, d, 2 × CH₃ of CH(CH₃)₂), 1.3 (3H, d, CH₃ of CHCH₃), 1.8 (1H, m, CH of CH(CH₃)₂), 2.4 (2H, d, CH₂ of CH₂CH(CH₃)₂), 3.2–3.4 (4H, s, CH₂ of OCH₂ and CH₂ of SCH₂), 3.6 (1H, q, CH of H₃CCHCO), 5.9 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.0–7.3 (8H, m, ArH), 10.0 (1H, s, NH of CONH), signal for OH of COOH could not be observed. Similarly, other compounds (**4a₁**-**a₁₁**, **a₁₃**-**a₁₅**, yields 62–78%) were prepared and crystallized from aqueous ethanol **4a₁**, m.p. 230°, **a₂**, 240°, **a₃**, 264°, **a₄**, 156°, **a₅**, 248°, **a₆**, 269°, **a₇**, 215°, **a₈**, 110°, **a₉**, 158°, **a₁₀**, 142°, **a₁₁**, 155°, **a₁₃**, 220°, **a₁₄**, 133°, **a₁₅**, 255°.

3,5-Disubstituted-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (5a₁₂) : Compound **3a₁₂** (0.1 mol) was treated with cold conc. H₂SO₄ whereby a pasty mass was obtained, which solidified on pouring into water. The solid was washed with water, dried and crystallized from aqueous ethanol : **5a₁₂** (78%), m.p. 117° (Found : C, 64.80; H, 6.16; N, 17.13. C₂₂H₂₅ON₅S calcd. : C, 64.86; H, 6.14; N, 17.18%); ν_{max} 3240 (NH₂), 2930 (OCH₂), 1610 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1010 cm⁻¹ (-O-); δ 0.9 (6H, d, 2 × CH₃ of CH(CH₃)₂), 1.3 (3H, d, CH₃ of CHCH₃), 1.8 (1H, m, CH of CH(CH₃)₂), 2.4 (2H, d, CH₂ of CH₂CH(CH₃)₂), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂ of OCH₂), 3.7 (1H, q, CH of CHCH₃), 5.9 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.0–7.4 (8H, m, ArH). Similarly, other compounds (**5a₁**-**a₁₁**, **a₁₃**-**a₁₅**, yields 64–80%) were prepared and crystallized from aqueous ethanol : **5a₁**, m.p. 108°, **a₂**, 247°, **a₃**, 256°, **a₄**, 200°, **a₅**, 110°, **a₆**, 130°, **a₇**, 175°, **a₈**, 198°, **a₉**, 140°, **a₁₀**, 135°, **a₁₁**, 190°, **a₁₃**, 140°, **a₁₄**, 155°, **a₁₅**, 112°.

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